

A hybrid optimization-based decision support system for cost-efficient pump scheduling in water supply systems

Marlene Brás^{a,b}, Ana Moura^a and António Andrade-Campos^b

^aDepartment of Economics, Management, Industrial Engineering and Tourism, GOVCOPP – Systems for Decision Support Research Group, University of Aveiro, Portugal

^bDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, Centre for Mechanical Technology & Automation (TEMA), Intelligent Systems Associate Laboratory (LASI), University of Aveiro, Portugal

E-mail: {marlenegomes, anamoura, gilac}@ua.pt

Keywords: *Nonlinear programming, Water Supply Systems, Pump Scheduling Problem, Decision System*

ABSTRACT

The rising global water demand, driven by population growth and urbanization, is placing increasing pressure on existing Water Supply Systems (WSS) (Burrow & Newman, 2020). Addressing this demand requires not only infrastructure expansion but also enhanced operational efficiency to reduce the high energy costs associated with water extraction, treatment, transport, and distribution. Pump operations constitute the largest share of energy consumption in WSS, accounting for up to 65% of total operational costs (Chen et al., 2021), making energy-efficient scheduling a key optimization challenge.

This study evaluates the performance of Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS), a hybrid optimization framework proposed by Brás et al. (2025) as a decision support system for minimizing energy costs in WSS. The method integrates deterministic local search with an intelligent shaking mechanism, designed to improve solution robustness and avoid local optima in dynamic operating conditions.

The framework is applied to a five-day case study involving a real WSS in Portugal. The optimization model, based on a duty-cycle formulation proposed in (Brás et al., 2024), considers operational constraints such as water tank levels, pump switching, and variable energy tariffs. Results indicate that Smart-DLS achieves substantial cost reductions, up to 24% daily and 19% overall, when compared to the real system operation, while maintaining compliance with all constraints.

The proposed methodology demonstrates flexibility in supporting different operational objectives, such as prioritizing cost efficiency or minimizing pump activations, and shows potential for real-world application, as daily optimized solutions are generated in under 10 minutes. These findings highlight Smart-DLS as a viable and scalable decision support approach for sustainable and energy-efficient pump scheduling in WSS.

Brás, M., Moura, A., & Andrade-campos, A. (2025). A Novel Hybrid Optimization Approach for Cost-Efficient Pump Scheduling in Water Supply Systems. *Omega*.

Brás, M., Moura, A., & Andrade-Campos, A. (2024). Cost efficiency in water supply systems: An applied review on optimization models for the pump scheduling problem. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 323(July 2024), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2024.07.039>

Burrow, A., & Newman, A. (2020). Optimal design and operation of River Basin Storage. *Omega*, 95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2019.04.004>

Chen, W., Tao, T., Zhou, A., Zhang, L., Liao, L., Wu, X., Yang, K., Li, C., Zhang, T. C., & Li, Z. (2021). Genetic optimization toward operation of water intake-supply pump stations system. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 279, 123573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123573>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the doctoral grant (Ref. 2022.12310.BD and DOI <https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.12310.BD>) financed by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), by the Regional Operational Program of the Center Region (CENTRO2030) within project I-ReTiS-LeaksD&Op (CENTRO2030-FEDER-01177300), and by the Research Unit on Governance, Competitiveness and Public Policies (UIDB/04058/2020) + (UIDP/04058/2020), funded by Portuguese funds through FCT.